

Green Plastics: A Necessity towards Sustainable Environment

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Abstract

Concern about the environment and its resources, especially the problems associated with environmental pollution is an important issue which has to be addressed seriously in every walk of life. These concerns are often not taken into consideration while measuring the strength or growth of an economy. The extent of pollution caused by human beings has been tremendously increasing especially if we come across plastic pollution. Plastics play a significant role in the sustainable construction of every nation. Modern lifestyles require more comfortable and easily disposable plastic products, but the accumulation of these non bio degradable products has aggravated the problem of pollution. As plastic is a source of toxic pollutants, it has the potential to disrupt the balance of ecosystem which is a great threat for plants, wildlife and human population. The toxic compounds present in plastics can leach deep into the soil horizon, thereby polluting ground water source and soil which makes the life of plants impossible. These harmful chemicals can interfere with the hormonal action in the body which will result in the break out of many diseases. Under such conditions, it is a necessity to explore ways to manufacture bio-degradable plastics which are also known as green plastics.

Introduction

Sustainable development often aims to balance our economic, environmental and social needs, allowing prosperity for the present and future generations. These include social progress and equality, environmental protection, conservation of natural resources and stable economic growth. In the light of heavy environmental crisis faced by all countries across the globe different eco-friendly concepts like green economy, green livelihood, green plastics, etc. are so relevant in today's world. Sustainable development, in particular, focuses on green GDP, green administration, renewable energy, green buildings and green homes, clean transportation, water management, waste management, and land management. If we consider most of the developed nations like the USA, they accept the concept of 'green' as an integral part of all their activities. In India, during the last few years, both central and state governments are much concerned with green concepts. Turning towards the state level, in the Emerging Kerala Project 2012 green concepts are much focused, and how to relate the three E's (environment, economy and equity) for attaining sustainability are much discussed.

Production, consumption, and distribution are the main threads that link the working of every economy. When we begin to make any product, the most relevant part of its production is its design itself, which indicates our choice of raw materials or scraps required to manufacture it. Our prime focus should be on that design which will surely throw light on one's views on sustainability. Therefore during the design itself, it is worthwhile to consider the end life of the product

also. Because this design itself focuses whether any particular product turns to be a curse or boon to the economy. In 2016, World plastic production totaled around 335million metric tons, and roughly half of the annual plastic production is destined for a single-use product. The principle cause of increasing plastic production is plastic packing. Plastic packing was 42 % of all nonfiber plastic production in 2015, and it also made up of 52% of plastic thrown away. Central Pollution Control Board report in 2014-15, revealed that 51.4 million tonnes of solid waste was generated in India, of which 91 percent was collected, and 27 percent was treated and remaining 73 percent disposed of at dump sites. As of 2015, approximately 6300 Mt of plastic waste has been generated, around 9% recycled, 12% incinerated, and 79% accumulated in landfills or the natural environment. In Kerala an order has been issued by the local self government department in the year 2016 banning plastic items below 50 microns. Yet no major action was taken by the majority of the local bodies to ban the sale of such plastic items. The data in 2018 showed that there is a production of 480 tonnes of plastic waste per day in the state which gives a vivid picture about the grim scenario discussed above.

The government of Kerala has made an expenditure of about Rs 2.5 crore over the past two years on awareness programs about the issues related with plastic pollution. The government ordered to use plastics for 10 percent of the roads built by local bodies in 2016-17. The target was doubled to 20 percent a year later but still the situation remains the same. According to Kerala Suchitwa Mission reports on an average, a family in Kerala produces 60 grams of plastic waste per day. Daily plastic waste production in Thiruvananthapuram municipal corporation is 26 tonnes, while Kochi and Kozhikode produce 16 tonnes each followed by Kollam (eight tonnes), Thrissur (seven tonnes) and Kannur (four tonnes).

Plastic waste generation thus is one of the complex issues nowadays as it emerges as a global problem for the environment and human health. The issues associated with wastes, especially plastic waste form a predominant threat to our environment which requires sufficient attention by the Government, NGO's and the public to think seriously and act accordingly to solve this problem to a great extent.

Giant molecules or polymers are principally used to produce plastics with the intention to protect foods, make lighter vehicles, household items, etc. But since the ancient past majority of such polymers are made from fossil fuels like polyethylene, polyester, polyvinylchloride, etc. It is evident that the light weight nature of plastics makes it economical in the packing and manufacturing industries, but the end life of such products creates an adverse impact upon the environment and as well as the sustainability of the economy.

The United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development popularly known as Rio+20 summit held in June 2012 at Rio de Janeiro, Brazil mainly under the influence of United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) discussed the topics related to the green economy, green growth, etc. The green economy can be defined as an economy which aims at alleviating environmental risks and promotes sustainable development. In the light of environmental crisis faced by all countries across the globe the concepts of green economy and green plastics need special attention. The term green economy was first proposed in a pioneering 1989 report for the Government of the United Kingdom by a group of leading environmental economists, which entitled a Blueprint for a Green Economy (Pearce, Markandya and Barbier, 1989). The Rio+20 summit stressed the principles for a green economy under the context of sustainable development and poverty eradication and tried to restore the global environment and give green livelihood for human beings by minimizing wastes. Green economy thus gives us a new economic growth paradigm friendly to environment and society and tries to maximize human wellbeing within environmental limits. A green economy according to Karl Burkart is based on six main sectors like renewable energy, green buildings, clean transportation, water management, waste management, and land management. A green economy is thus a clean energy economy; consist of renewable energy like solar, wind, thermal, green building and green infrastructure and transportation and more importantly recycling of waste-to-energy. Nature is invaluable, and all living beings have the right to live in this world; therefore the role of waste disposal has a significant role in the green economy. Under this context, it is inevitable that every economy tries eco-friendly industries, which often aims at clean air, clean water, and clean environment.

In a green economy the concept of green GDP is of foremost importance, and in 2009 the then environment minister Jairam Ramesh started an initiative to estimate green GDP under the leadership of Pronab Sen. Similarly, United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (UNCSD) states that “The concept of green economy focuses primarily on the intersection between environment and economy” (United Nations 2010). Green economy thus recognizes the right to development, development needs and priorities along with social development which includes livelihood issues and poverty eradication. By this we can point out the three main pillars upon which the concept of green economy rests on:

1. Environmental protection,
2. Economic development,
3. Social development.

Green economy gives more importance to use value than exchange value and thus maintains economies of quality by minimizing waste and recycling it. If we consider most of the developed nations today like the USA, they accept the concept of ‘green’ as an integral part of all their activities even in administration. Green economy is thus the aggregate of all those activities operating with the aim of minimizing all forms of environmental impact. Turning to India, the concept of green economy is popularised by many centers like AKRUTI (The Advanced Knowledge and Rural Technology Implementation centers) mainly designed by Baba Atomic Research Centre in many Indian villages made them aware to use clean drinking water, how to turn waste to degradable form and so on. Along with this KRUTIK (Knowledge and Rural Technology Implementation Kendra) helps farmers to adopt suitable technologies in their fields mainly that of green technologies.

This paper mainly focuses on plastic, plastic waste and the role of green plastics in a green economy. In Kerala, waste disposal is always a problem, and its grave effects are accentuated mainly in the case of nondegradable plastics. Kerala imposed a ban on the use of plastic carry bags with a thickness of less than 30 microns in 2003, and the government is also taking measures to deal with non degradable plastic wastes and prevent the misuse of plastics but the problem of scrap persists, and it is essential that the Kerala government seriously consider the need for developing green plastics.

Role of plastics in an economy

Plastics are found everywhere in today’s human lifestyle and it forms an integral part of our day to day life. Because of its durability and capacity to mould easily, the use of plastics is manifold. About 100 million tons of plastics are produced worldwide every year and every sector of Indian economy whether agriculture, industry or the service sector to a great extent depend upon plastics for its development. A brief history about the evolution, and composition of plastics is crucial on a journey to develop green plastics to promote sustainability. Plastics are synthetic substance produced by chemical reaction, and all most all types of traditional plastics are made from petroleum and are not biodegradable. They are polymers with very long

chain molecules which consist of subunits called monomers, and the monomers of petrochemical plastics are inorganic like ethylene, styrene, vinyl chloride, and propylene, etc. Thus plastics are a unique combination of molecules which are fused through heat or pressure to form different materials. It was Dr. L. H. Baekeland in 1909 developed phenol-formaldehyde plastic which is commonly known as Bakelite and from there started a new era of synthetic plastic industry.

Plastics can be divided under two heads: thermosets and thermoplastics. A thermoset plastic is like concrete, and we can get only one chance to liquefy and mould, and on the other hand thermoplastic is like wax, and we can use it and alter it several times. The Thermoplastics are recyclable plastics which include; Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), Low-density Poly Ethylene (LDPE), Poly Vinyl Chloride(PVC), High-Density Poly Ethylene (HDPE), Polypropylene(PP), Polystyrene (PS), etc.

- Plastic wastes: Adverse effects

In Kerala, we can find the scraps have been piled over certain areas, and frequent fires in the dumping areas generate environmental pollution, and the residential area nearby faces so many problems including health as well as social issues. When people have no waste management services, they can only dump plastic waste in the open or burn it. Open burning of plastic waste is quite sad and it will create environmental issues and health problems. Poisonous chemicals released by the burning of plastics can cause respiratory problems upon inhalation by humans and animals.

Plastic wastes come from different sources like:

- a. Carry bags, and packages
- b. Water bottles
- c. Disposals from hospitals, and medical shops
- d. Railways, and airways
- e. Hotels, and catering services

Thermoplastics constitutes 80% and thermoset approximately 20% of total plastic waste generated in India. Environmental pollution due to these wastes is a global phenomenon today. Low-Density Poly Ethylene (LDPE), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Poly Ethylene Terephthalate (PET), Polypropylene (PP) are the main types of plastic wastes. The burning of polyurethane foam releases about 57 cancer-causing chemicals. Many of our food items including milk are sold in plastic sachets which use polyvinyl chloride (PVC) which is a known carcinogen. Plastic debris in the water too creates serious environmental problems.

Impact of plastics on human health

Fossil fuel based traditional plastic products often generate adverse health hazards, and among them, Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polystyrene create the worst effects. Studies reveal that it will cause cancer, adversely affect the endocrine system, overall it will affect future generation through genetic disorders. Polystyrene made from benzene is carcinogenic, and styrene too has the same effect. According to the International Plastics Task Force plastic often releases certain harmful chemicals like bisphenol A. Bisphenol A which is a chemical compound found more in clear plastic containers like plastic cups and baby bottles. When we expose the plastic containers to heat, synthetic chemicals will be released to the foodstuffs, and this is called leaching, and it will cause harmful side effects. If we microwave polycarbonate plastic food containers, it releases BPA and, creates many health issues. The containers used to house fish and meat too creates allergies and other respiratory problems. It also causes genital abnormalities and even a decline in the quality and count of human sperm. Similarly different types of plastics used in food packaging also lead to chronic bronchitis, ulcers and liver dysfunction.

Three Polymers to Avoid

Polymer	Common Applications	Health Issues
Polycarbonate (PC)	Baby bottles, sports water bottles	Can leach out bisphenol A, a hormone disruptor
Polystyrene (PS)	Foam insulation, packaging peanuts, plastic utensils, meat trays, egg cartons, take-out containers, single-use disposable cups	Uses benzene, styrene and 1,3-butadiene. Styrene is a neurotoxin and is known to be toxic to the reproductive system. PS releases toxic chemicals when burned.
Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC or vinyl)	Building pipes, siding, membrane roofing, flooring, and window frame; shower curtains, beach balls, credit cards, cooking oil bottles	Made from the vinyl chloride monomer; high chlorine and additive content. Toxic additives such as phthalate softeners leach out. PVC releases dioxin and other persistent organic pollutants.

Sources: <http://bioplasticsinfo.com/problems-with-plastics/>
 Healthy Building Network's Guide to Plastic Lumber (2005),
 Creating Safe and Healthy Spaces: Selecting Materials that Support Healing (2006),
 Center for Health, Environment, and Justice's PVC - Bad News Comes in 3s (2004)

a. Impact of plastics on the environment

Plastic bags emit dangerous greenhouse gases, and when we burn, it emits toxic gases and heavy metals which in turn results in ecological imbalance. Plastic bags are being made from two types of plastics namely high-density polyethylene, and low-density polyethylene, and the former can be easily recycled. Among different types of plastic waste materials, plastic bags form the prime category and the amount used annually worldwide is about 4 and 5 trillion, and only 0.6 percent of plastic bags are being recycled. Green bags are one way to make sure that plastic degrades into the earth instead of harming the environment. Plastic waste accounts for about 60 to 80 percent of the waste in water. To know about the intensity of plastic waste in water, The Pacific Ocean Garbage Patch is a good example. Out of the 3.5 million tons of trash in the Pacific Ocean garbage patch, 80 percent is plastic and 86 percent of sea turtle species suffer from plastic marine debris. Seventy percent of earth surface has been filled with water and majority of these wastes can lead to the pollution of oceans, and sufficient attention is to be given to recycle these wastes as far as possible and there comes the necessity of green plastics. Adding to that when these wastes are consumed by birds and marine organisms, they can't survive and their population will be reduced drastically. Plastic bags do not allow water and oxygen to ooze underground, and thus make the depletion of same and makes soil infertile.

Disposal of plastic wastes

a. Recycling

We can manage the effects of plastic wastes by recycling them and try to minimize the use of plastics. Plastic recycling industry and efficient waste management are essential for our Kerala too where the problem of waste stood at the forefront of the issues faced by our state.

List of registered plastic recycling units in Kerala, November 2017

Sl.No.	Name of the District	No: of Units
1	Thiruvananthapuram	2
2	Kollam	11
3	Pathanamthitta	2

4	Alappuzha	1
5	Kottayam	3
6	Ernakulam	51
7	Palakkad	1
8	Thrissur	10
9	Kozhikode	12
10	Malappuram	3
11	Kannur	4
12	Kasargod	2

Source: Kerala State Pollution Control board Report, 2018

While talking about recycling, we should be careful whether it is first, second or third recycling as the number goes on increasing the proportion of virgin plastic goes on diminishing, and the waste pickers know the quality, and price they gain from these waste and they reject the plastics with low virgin plastic contents which increased landfills.

b. Pyrolysis

We can dispose of plastic waste through Pyrolysis technique and can develop environmental friendly products. Pyrolysis is the thermal degradation of waste in an oxygen-starved environment.

c. Incineration

In Kerala, we face the problem of electricity shortage, and frequent current cut problems, conversion of plastic waste into liquid fuel just like the model adopted in Maharashtra can be used here too. For this purpose collection and segregation, storing and shredding of wastes followed by heating the plastic wastes to 2700 c to 3000 c. Such heating converts plastic waste in the form of vapor in the presence of a catalyst which can be converted into organic gas, later used in the generation of electricity and whatever left after that is the tarry waste which can be used for road construction. Even incineration is not a sustainable solution to plastic waste, when plastic has been burnt the carbon content is turned to carbon dioxide which is a greenhouse gas. Along with these so many toxic gases, and solid wastes are released. Burning PVC releases at least 75 by-products of combustion including carcinogens like vinyl chloride, etc.

d. Landfills

Landfills and associated fires have many adverse effects on the environment, and in the society.

e. Bio degradation and Green plastics: A sustainable Solution to plastic wastes

Biodegradation or biotic degradation is the dissolution of wastes with the help of microorganisms like bacteria, algae, fungi, etc. Such biodegradable matter is mainly organic material like plant and animal matter or other substances originating from living organisms. Today most commonly we use Teflon coated nonstick pans and many are unaware that Teflon gives off toxic but odorless fumes when heated to a high temperature, and it adversely affects our respiratory systems. It too is nondegradable, and causes environmental pollution. Developed economies now tried to recycle low-density polyethylene (LDPE) plastic bags. Use of these wastes in road construction can alleviate the problem of pollution and disposal problems. Plastics like polyethylene, polypropylene, and polystyrene when heated at 100-160 degree celsius exhibit good binding principles, and by such properties test roadways were laid down in south Indian states like Kerala, and the response was good, and the roads made up of such plastic wastes have good standing capacity. Polymer coated bitumen road to a great extent solved our problem on roadways. Compared to the conventional roads such polymer mixed ones have twice standing capacity and even in the rainy season, we need fewer repairs because water does not sweep through plastics in the tar. Plastic water bottles pose another major problem faced by Kerala, where tourists as well as native people demand bottled water at a high rate. The problems associated with such water bottles are often neglected and there is an increasing need for water bottles

which are eco-friendly. There is need for Bio plastic water bottles like that of which made by Green Planet an American company which is 100% plant-based, toxin-free, and carbon neutral as against those bottles which contain petroleum and BPA. Similarly, companies like Keystone Water Company (USA), Nestle and PepsiCo all are now developing green plastics which are 100 percent degradable and recyclable.

Green Plastics and Sustainable Development

Green plastics are generally plant-derived polymers, produced by converting plant sugars into plastic, inside microorganisms (bacteria), or growing the plastic inside the leaves or stalk of corn or other crops. Green plastics are mainly a form of plastics derived from renewable biomass sources like vegetable oils and fats, corn starch, pea starch, microbiota, etc. These types of plastics gained momentum mainly from the development of green chemistry as it stressed all products at the end of their function should be capable of breaking into degradable products. Under such a notion plastics can be classified into degradable, nondegradable, and compostable plastics. Conventional plastics are non biodegradable which can't be used as a food source by any living creature. If such plastics are made green, it can be degraded into carbon dioxide, methane, water and inorganic compounds. They are non-toxic and disappear rapidly with a maximum span of 6 months. Cellophane was the first biodegradable plastic produced in 1908, and among the major types of green plastics came from cellulose-based plastics. Green plastics can be made from natural starch-based polymers like thermoplastic starch-based polymers made with 90 percent starch from renewable resources such as corn, potato, wheat, tapioca etc. Green plastics promote sustainability and reduce our dependence on fossil fuels, not only this but also green plastics are cheaper than fossil fuel based traditional plastics. If we shift in favor of green plastics it will help us to cleanse our state from the dubious waste problem, more suited to public as it is a low cost program, and it can reduce our morbidity rate which had shown a drastic increase associated with the use of fossil fuel based plastics.

The components of Green plastics are derived from renewable raw materials found in nature which helps to maintain environmental stability, and enable every nation to walk through a path of sustainable development. It mainly uses polymers from agriculture and marine feedstocks and plastics made from such materials are biodegradable. Green plastics are purely natural in origin, and some examples of green plastics are PLA (Polylactic acid), PHB/V (Polyhydroxybutyrate covalerate) commercially marketed under the trade name Biopol, Starch based plastics, PCL (Polycaprolactone), etc. PLA are transparent plastics produced from cane sugar or glucose, and it is difficult to recycle. PHB/V is a polyester produced by certain bacteria on glucose, cornstarch, and wastewater. Similarly, starch-based plastics made up of starch-based polymers from crops like maize, wheat, potatoes, banana peels, etc also have much impact on the environment. PCL has so many biomedical uses and it has specific applications in the human body. In Kerala, the Mar Athanasios College for Advanced Studies Thiruvalla (Macfast), under the guidance of Dr. Balagopalan, the former dean and director of Mac fast school of Biosciences has developed bioplastics through powdered cellulose obtained from natural fibers such as jute and water hyacinth. The organic content include in the plastics is easily degradable, and the cellulose molecules are consumed by microbes when it is disposed of. Such types of plastics are noted for its strength as well as environmental friendly approach, and help in sustainable development. For example, toothbrushes with neem hand stick and nylon bristles were developed which are most suited to our health and nylon is degraded with the help of nylon eating bacteria, Flavobacteria and Pseudomonas found in 1975. All green plastics made from natural resources like cellulose, starch, soy protein polyesters, etc are easily degradable when exposed to air and sun.

Researchers at Manonmaniam Sundaranar University in Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, have found that the water hyacinth, which is often considered as an invasive weed is a rich source of carbohydrates that can be used to make biodegradable plastic. Water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) derived sugar molecules like lignin, cellulose and hemicelluloses can be converted into polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB). It is a raw material for making biodegradable plastics. Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) is a polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA), a polymer

belonging to the polyesters class that are of interest as bio-derived and biodegradable plastics. Plastics developed using PHB are compostable, and can reduce green house effects. To make PHB, researchers dried and crushed water hyacinth into a fine powder and subjected it to hydrolytic treatment. Using the end product, *Cupriavidus necator*, a bacterium known to produce PHB was cultured in the presence of organic and inorganic nitrogen sources. Accumulation of PHB was noted inside them. Bacterial cells were made to lyse using an alkaline solution and extracted the PHB. Maximum PHB, 4.3 grams per liter, was obtained from the bacteria cultured using the products of enzymatic breakdown of water hyacinth powder. In Kerala, we often blame the unnecessary growth of the notorious weed Water hyacinth in water bodies, but it is a good source to produce green plastics.

Green plastics promote sustainability and reduce our dependence on fossil fuels. Production technique which is much cheaper to produce plastics in a more ecofriendly manner than the traditional fossil fuel based plastics should be welcomed in our state. Kerala always considered as a model in many fields of activity should promote the consumption and production of green plastics for a sustainable future.

Conclusion

GDP in green terms, the Green Gross Domestic Product (green GDP) is an index of economic growth by considering the environment. Some environmental experts prefer physical indicators (such as “waste per capita” or “carbon dioxide emissions per year”), which may be aggregated to form indices such as the “Sustainable Development Index.” But as a first step, in order to reduce the environmental impact of plastics first of all we have to minimize its use, shift to reusable plastics rather than disposable one, and government regulations through necessary legislations to make standardized labels for recycled, recyclable, disposable, etc will reduce the intensity of the problem of plastic wastes. Governments should put forward sufficient legislation to prohibit the selling of plastics contains microns less than the prescribed microns. Along with this the use of paper bags and bags made of bio degradable materials like jute, cotton, etc should be promoted through media. The burning of plastic waste in incinerator centers causes air pollution.

Therefore, an efficient research should be done to develop suitable technologies to reduce pollution associated with burning of nonrecyclable plastics. Efforts for efficient plastic waste management should also come from the side of civilians too. Whatever are the legislations undertaken from the side of government will not be fruitful if the citizens of the concerned areas are not cooperating. We the civilians should be very keen to throw plastics in garbage and dustbins and not leaving them in public places and follow government regulations strictly. In an agrarian economy like ours, we are using plastic banana leaves for feasts which creates a tremendous amount of wastes after the functions.

If we turn towards natural and eco-friendly products like jute, coir, natural leaves our economy can be converted to green to a great extent. The Government should take sufficient measures to promote research in the area of green plastics which make our Kerala clean and toxin-free area which will provide a better quality of life for the people. Through the adoption of green plastics and green economy, we can make our green Kerala ‘green’ in the real sense.

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